

PRINCIPLES OF CHILD SPEECH DEVELOPMENT THROUGH ENVIRONMENT INTRODUCTION

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One of the main tasks of the preschool education organization is to form the correct oral speech of children as a result of mastering the artistic language of their people. This general task consists of the following special tasks: education of sound culture of speech, enrichment, strengthening and activation of vocabulary, improvement of grammatical correctness of speech, formation of oral (dialogic) speech, development of fluent speech, education of interest in artistic words, is preparation for teaching literacy. It is necessary to implement the development of children's speech on the basis of an appropriate program. In this program, the range of knowledge about the environment and the size of the vocabulary, speech skills and skills that should be formed in children at each age stage are determined, and it aims to educate certain qualities of the person (approachability, politeness, modesty). should hold. The speech development program is based on scientific principles, and it is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's personality with all its content. The speech development program is implemented in the forms of the child's activity, such as study, play, work and household activities. In the context of public education, education is the leading means of forming a child's speech. Teaching the mother tongue is a process of planning and purposeful development of the child's cognitive abilities, the formation of their basic knowledge of the world around them and the acquisition of relevant vocabulary, and the formation of speech skills and abilities.

The main form of education for children of preschool age is training. For didactic purposes, the following types of training can be distinguished: - training on introducing new material; - trainings related to strengthening knowledge, skills and abilities; - exercises related to generalization and systematization of knowledge; - final exercises or assessment (control) exercises. It is recommended to conduct exercises for the development of speech of children from 1 to 3 years old in the form of didactic games, fun games, and stage performances. They should be not only entertaining, but also educational. The development of children's speech between 3 and 5 years old should have an

emotional tone. It is necessary to widely use exhibitionism, game methods and didactic games. Speech development activities for children aged 5 to 7 years have a specific task - that is, it aims to prepare children for studying at school.

During the training, the pedagogue should develop the ability to carry out educational activities in addition to speech tasks (to be attentive, listen to the pedagogue's task, understand it and carry it out clearly, be able to think in front of a group of children, respond to a peer's answer can perform the task of being able to give a simple assessment, etc.). Positive results can be achieved if the best qualities acquired by the child in the preschool educational institution are continued in the family environment and the best qualities acquired in the family are applied in the preschool educational institution. Educators should not only see the positive results of their experience in family education, but also support it and, on this basis, focus the attention of parents on tasks that have not yet been solved in child education. The head is the person responsible for planning, organizing and leading the above work. An annual plan for working with parents will be drawn up. This plan will be discussed in the pedagogical council. The plan includes general and group meetings, open-door days for parents, talks and consultations, organizing exhibitions and concerts in parenting organizations, as well as determining the times of these events and the persons responsible for them. possible The topics and content of the work with parents are reflected in the educator-methodist's plan and the educator's calendar plan. A lot of work on working with parents is done by the educator - pedagogue, because he sees more than anyone else the changes that are taking place in the upbringing of the child and is closely familiar with the life of children. It gives recommendations to parents on what to pay more attention to in the education of children, preparation for school education, health care, proper organization of food and daily routine, etc. 2. Contents of the preschool educational institution's work in cooperation with parents. The headmaster, team of pedagogues and parents should actively participate in cooperation between educational institutions and schools.

Only then can the expected results in child education be achieved. The following special forms of work are used in working with parents: conversations, consultations, visiting families, inviting some parents to the preschool, using separate memorabilia and portable folders. The purpose of visiting the child's home is to learn about the family conditions, the child's behavioral interests in the family, to get to know the parents and family members, as well as to introduce the parents to the effective methods of child

education, and to study and publicize the positive experience of the family in child education. The educator should go to the child's house not as an inspector, but as a friend, a helper in the difficult task of raising a child, and should treat family members with kindness and courtesy. Before each visit to each family, the educator should set a clear goal and determine in advance what topic he will talk about. Questions to parents should be carefully thought out. The conversation should be structured in such a way that the tutor and parents understand each other well, and there should be a reliable communication between them. Before visiting a family, the educator should have certain ideas about this family (the character of the parents, family relations, the child's level of development). In order to gain the respect and trust of the parents, the educator first learns the opinions and comments of the parents about the positive qualities of the child and how to organize the life of the child at home, what can be read and told to him, the child's schedule, can make recommendations on the content and methods of educational work, such as involving him in family work, raising him in the spirit of respect for adults. Of course, the educator's work with the family takes into account the child's age, capabilities, and unique characteristics. The purpose and content of the visit to the family should be reflected in the educator's plan and report, as well as in his diary. The content of the work carried out with parents is varied, and it is necessary to discuss some issues together. For example: the role of the family in raising children, the role of parents, laws on preparing children for school; on the annual work plan of preschool education institutions; the issues of the work of the parents' community are among them. Forms of work such as groups of parents and general meetings, consultations, conferences, parents' evenings for discussing this issue as a team are included in the forms of team work. Parents meeting. Parents of all groups of children, parents of parallel groups and parents of children of one group can be invited to the meeting of parents. At the general meeting, parents will be introduced to the tasks of comprehensive development and upbringing of children of preschool age, this year's plans, activities of the parents' committee, best practices in family education. At the meeting, the headmaster or a Methodist educator will give a speech, parents will speak, and children will speak. These allow to identify achievements and shortcomings in education, strengthen family and public relations, increase the responsibility of parents for the education of their child, and arouse interest in preschool educational institutions. At the meeting of parents in the group, the issues that are relevant for the parents of children of this age are discussed. For example, if the topic of

the general meeting is "The role of the family in moral education of children", then this topic will be complicated in the meeting held in the middle group, and the topics will be "Joint work of educational institutions and the family in raising diligence in children", "Education of respect for adults in children" and etc. can be. A lecture prepared for parents can be combined with children's work, a film on a related topic, and viewing slides.

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